

Dendrochronological analysis of samples from shipwreck BC17 found at Barcode, Oslo NMM 03010119

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Samples from shipwreck BC17, found during archaeological excavations at Barcode in Oslo, have been submitted for dendrochronological analysis in several instalments. The boat is one of 17 boats found and excavated at this site, over the past several years, and these are currently the subject of ongoing dendrochronological analysis (for example Daly 2010, 2011c). Most of the Barcode boats are dating to the second half of the 16th century. One sample from BC17 was previously dated, and a small number of samples from barrel parts used as repair patches were also analysed and dated. These analyses demonstrated that the ship was built of timber felled after AD 1353 (Daly 2013a) while the repairs were made using barrel parts that were from trees felled in AD 1343-55 (x401) and AD 1347-60 (x402) (Daly 2013b).

Fig. 1. Barcode ship BC17, Oslo. Result of the dendrochronological dating analysis.

In 2015 an additional 10 samples were submitted, six of *Quercus sp.*, oak and four conifer, all of which have been identified as *Pinus sp.*, pine. In total then, 13 samples from the ship and two repair pieces have been analysed.

For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the *t*-value ("*t*-test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed.

The dated oak

Of the nine oak timbers from the ship, only two are successfully dated; plank x203, (Z095001a, previously reported) and plank x177 (Z095206a). The tree-ring curves from the two match together, with a correlation value (t -value) of $t = 5.39$. Four sapwood rings are preserved on plank x177. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that was used to make this plank can be placed at **AD 1350-62** (marked in green, fig. 1).

As this tree grew in the Southern Baltic region (see below) a sapwood statistic for Poland is used. Here oak trees have an average of 15 sapwood years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990).

Filenames	-	-	Z0952M01	
-	start	dates	AD1190	
-	dates	end	AD1345	
Site and master chronologies				
PM670108	AD725	AD1985	6,83	Gdansk (Wazny pers comm.)
0704002s	AD1151	AD1363	6,58	Jeziernik (Wazny pers comm.)
P671002S	AD982	AD1295	6,44	Elblag (Wazny pers comm.)
PUCKM002	AD1134	AD1329	6,32	Puck (Wazny pers comm.)
O0700049	AD801	AD1496	6,20	Lund (Bartholin pers comm)
SM000001	AD651	AD1496	6,11	Sydvestskaane (Bartholin pers comm)
0M040004	AD1156	AD1597	6,04	Baltic 1 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
DM200004	30BC	AD1960	5,98	G Weser (Göttingen University)
PP123M01	AD1049	AD1311	5,98	Elblag 43 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP103M01	AD1136	AD1335	5,90	Gdansk Ratusz 10 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
Baltic timber (ships, barrels, boards, decorative panels etc.)				
HMC_T165	AD1078	AD1369	8,09	Hull boards from 37 coffins Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm.)
CLS2000	AD1110	AD1393	7,37	Boat, Hull, Chapel Lane Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm.)
Z076m001	AD1097	AD1393	7,08	Skjernøysund 3 (Daly 2011b)
Z005M003	AD1063	AD1373	6,80	Bølevraget planks (Daly & Nymoer 2008)
0056M001	AD1174	AD1335	6,79	Aberdeen Barrel (Crone pers comm.)
02071M01	AD1126	AD1414	6,47	Dokøen; Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001)
Z056m001	AD1065	AD1266	6,38	Egelskärsvraket Finland barrel 4 timbers (Daly 2011a)
se617M01	AD1100	AD1396	6,37	New Baxtergate Grims (Tyers pers comm.)
Z034m001	AD1188	AD1371	6,30	Bovet Læsø vrag WM2294 (Daly unpubl. 2009)

Table 1. Barcode ship BC17, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the mean curve Z0952M01 (average of samples x203 (Z095001a) and x177 (Z095206a)) and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

In table 1 the correlation values (t -values) between the average curve from the two dated oak planks and a selection of Northern European master and site chronologies are shown. The curve from the planks dates best with tree-ring data from a range of chronologies from the Baltic Sea region, and with data from structures (shipwrecks, barrels, boards etc.) that have been shown, through dendrochronological analysis, to be made from oaks from the Southern Baltic region.

The two barrel parts used as repairs are reported previously and are from trees felled in AD 1343-55 and AD 1347-60 respectively (fig. 1), and both trees grew in the Southern Baltic region (Daly 2013b).

The dated pine

Of the four pine samples analysed, three are dated. The tree-ring curves from two samples achieve a correlation of $t = 5.98$ while the third only matches very weakly with the two (see table 2). An average of these three (Z0953M01) was made which is 175 years in length, and covers the period AD 1171-1345. The pine samples are dating with a range of Scandinavian pine datasets (table 3). The outermost preserved tree-ring on the dated pine samples was formed in 1345, and bark edge was not preserved on these samples. The pine trees that these samples come from were felled **after AD 1346** (marked in orange, fig. 1). This result fits very well with the dating of the two oak samples.

		Z0953019	Z0953029	Z095303a
X100	Z0953019	*	2,48	2,00
X161	Z0953029	2,48	*	5,98
X146	Z095303a	2,00	5,98	*

Table 2. Barcode ship BC17, Oslo. The correlation between the tree-ring curves from the three dated pine samples with each other. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Filenames	-	-	Z0953M01	
-	start	dates	AD1171	
-	dates	end	AD1345	
Master chronologies pine				
Dalpinus	AD931	AD1888	8,26	Dalarna (Eggertsson pers comm)
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	6,63	Gotland Pinus ((Bartholin pers comm)
SMAPIN02	AD989	AD1344	4,90	Småland Lofstrand (Bartholin pers comm)
30710039	AD995	AD1322	4,68	Nordbergs Haebre (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_HL1	AD1001	AD1861	4,51	Helsingland Pinus (Bartholin pers comm)

Table 3. Barcode ship BC17, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the mean curve Z0953M01 (average of the pine samples x100 (Z0953019), x161 (Z0953029) & x146 (Z095303a)) and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

The undated samples

Disappointingly, of the 13 samples from the ship structure, eight could not be dated. For some of these this is due to the relatively few rings preserved, but four of the undated oak samples contain sufficiently long tree-ring series, and due to their internal cross-matching (table 4 & fig. 2) form a very clear group. A visual match between this group and a fifth sample is also made (fig. 2).

		Z0950039	Z0950029	Z095202a	Z095203a
X207 keel	Z0950039	*	4,23	5,84	5,10
X9	Z0950029	4,23	*	8,65	5,00
X112	Z095202a	5,84	8,65	*	7,08
X180	Z095203a	5,10	5,00	7,08	*

Table 4. Barcode ship BC17, Oslo. The correlation between the tree-ring curves from four undated oak samples with each other. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Fig. 2. Barcode ship BC17, Oslo. The **relative** positions of the tree-ring curves from the samples that form the undated oak group.

An average of the tree-ring curves from the four samples that form the undated oak group has been made (Z0952M02) and this is 131 years long, but this cannot currently be dated. It is possible that these structural components come from trees that grew in a region for which sufficient oak chronologies for the period are not available.

The dendrochronological analysis of this ship demonstrates that there was a wide mixture of timbers that were used in her building. The keel and several planks form one, unfortunately undated group, which might indicate one timber source. The dated oak is demonstrating a Southern Baltic provenance, while pine planks are clearly dating with Scandinavian datasets. It is hoped that the undated oak group, which includes the keel timber, can be dated in the future, to attain an indication of where these timbers grew.

Literature

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave ring width	Interpretation / felling
Z095001a	Barcode Norge NMM 03010119 bord x203 QUSP	154	AD1190	AD1343	G	0	N	R	H1	1.61	after AD1353
Z0950029	Barcode Norge NMM 03010119 bord x9 QUSP	131			G	11	N	T	N	0.86	Undated
Z0950039	Barcode Norge NMM 03010119 køl x207 QUSP	114			C	0	N	O	N	1.10	Undated
Z095101a	Barcode17 Norge NMM 03010119 repair barrel x401 QUSP	200	AD1147	AD1346	G	10	N	R	S1	0.75	AD1347-60
Z095102a	Barcode17 Norge NMM 03010119 repair barrel x402 QUSP	159	AD1184	AD1342	G	11	N	R	S1	0.89	AD1343-55
Z095201a	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 hudbord x218 p415 QUSP	42			V	9	N	T	S1	2.10	Undated
Z095202a	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 hudbord x112 p416 QUSP	124			F	5	N	T	S1	0.87	Undated
Z095203a	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 hudbord x180 p419 QUSP	108			G	11	N	T	S1	0.97	Undated
Z095204a	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 forstevn x176 p420 QUSP	104			G	0	N	O	H1	0.80	Undated
Z0952059	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 akterstevn x182 p421 QUSP	61			V	7	N	O	S1	1.60	undated
Z095206a	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 hudbord x177 p422 QUSP	111	AD1235	AD1345	G	4	N	R	S1	2.08	AD1350-62
Z0953019	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 hudbord x100 p403 PISY	175	AD1171	AD1345	F	0	N	T	N	0.75	after AD1346
Z0953029	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 hudbord x161 p417 PISY	109	AD1231	AD1339	F	0	N	T	N	1.07	after AD1340
Z095303a	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 hudbord x146 p418 PISY	119	AD1221	AD1339	F	0	N	T	H1	1.03	after AD1341
Z095304a	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 bunnstok x053 p423 PISY	43			C	0	N	S	N	2.53	undated
Z0952M01	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 2 timbers QUSP	156	AD1190	AD1345						1.83	
Z0952M02	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 4 timbers QUSP	131								0.93	
Z0953M01	Barcode 17 BC17 Norge NMM 03010119 3 timbers PISY	175	AD1171	AD1345						0.99	

Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.
 Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.

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